
Research Dream Team Toolkit

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Research Dream Team

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This toolkit is a resource intended to make it as easy as possible to organise a workshop aimed at raising awareness of and facilitating discussion around the diversity of roles that contribute to research.

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1.1 About the toolkit

This toolkit is a resource intended to make it as easy as possible to organise a workshop aimed at raising awareness of and facilitating discussion around the diversity of roles that contribute to research.

1.1.1 Why is the topic important?

In recent years, there has been an increased perception of the potential for interdisciplinary and collaborative research to address complex societal and environmental needs. It is also becoming increasingly clear that a diversity of roles and contributions is needed to drive progress and success in research and innovation.

Realising it is no longer the case - if it ever was - that all researchers need to - or indeed can - have all of the skills needed to find answers to large and complex societal questions, the knowledge sector is now looking towards a team-based approach bringing together more overtly diverse team members with specific skills in funding, research design, data analysis, data management, software development, research ethics, political relationships, dealing with business, interdisciplinarity, communications etc.

What does this new thinking mean in practice? What skills are needed to successfully carry out research today? How are different teams composed, managed and rewarded? Can research morph from a sector where only ‘star researchers’ are appreciated to one where everyone, including professional support staff, is recognised for their skills and contributions?

This toolkit helps put together and organise a workshop that explores what a dream research team might look like and discuss what this might mean for how research is supported, managed and rewarded.

1.1.2 Why this toolkit?

The authors organised a workshop on this topic at the [Dutch National Open Science Festival 2022](#), which led to a lot of engagement and discussion. Subsequently, the organisers received requests from colleagues at other institutions to host similar workshops. Rather than organising further workshops, we felt it would be more useful and more sustainable to provide others with the tools and information necessary to organise their own workshops. Therefore, we created this toolkit to support anyone who wishes to organise similar future workshops and to make it as easy as possible for them to do so.

1.1.3 For whom?

This toolkit is for anyone who would like to facilitate discussion and raise awareness about diversity of roles and contributions to research in an inclusive and interactive way.

1.2 Contents

The toolkit is composed of the following elements:

- *About the toolkit*: Description of the toolkit.
- *Goals and possible outcomes*: Goals and possible outcomes of the workshop.
- *Practicalities*: Information about specific organisational aspects related to this workshop.
- *Agenda*: an actionable and re-usable workshop agenda, with some practical tips, which you might use to support your own workshop.
- *Scenario*: During the workshop the participants will be presented with a fictional research project (a scenario) that will underpin their discussions about the composition and skills that the ideal research team will need to have to tackle that particular project. This toolkit offers one possible scenario to support such a discussion, shares some insights which might help you develop an alternative scenario to suit your needs, and also offers some guidance for facilitating the discussion.
- *Activity*: A step by step explanation of the workshop activity.
- *Slide Deck*: Presentation template which you can use to introduce the workshop, the scenario and the breakout activities
- *Activity Sheet*: Printout copy of an activity sheet that each breakout group can use to facilitate their discussion. Print them out in a large format (e.g. A0).

1.3 Goals and possible outcomes

The primary goal of the workshop is to start the discussion and raise awareness by getting researchers and professional support staff together in one room collaboratively thinking about the skills and roles needed for effectively tackling complex research questions. Participants will leave with an increased awareness of the many skills, experiences and roles that contribute to the success of the research system.

For instance, during our first workshop at the [2022 Edition of the Netherlands National Open Science Festival](#), many insights were shared. Ideas such as the need for traditional support to move from ‘answer as questions come in’ towards embedding expertise within the faculty/school/group, based on the idea that if you build a relationship, you can achieve so much more than with central, anonymous support. And that what is needed for this is a change from project management thinking (finite, disconnected) to more integral programs and continuous change and value based working is needed. Project goals should be better linked to larger goals, which are often mentioned in the strategy of universities, but are not easy to find in the actual projects. Moreover, while discussing these kinds of new approaches, it is important to rethink how to successfully engage with other colleagues and build effective collaborations. For instance, values like shared ownership can help to engage larger teams; people then feel connected to the project as a whole, even when they are responsible for just a small task. Above all, all participants stressed the importance of appreciating everyone’s contributions.

By discussing these points with others in the workshop, participants are likely to start thinking differently about research teams and how these teams are supported, managed and rewarded. At least a small proportion of the participants may feel motivated to take this thinking further - either through specific actions within their own sphere of influence, and/or through engaging in broader activities aiming at enhanced cooperation, synergies, and transdisciplinary collaboration.

The topics discussed in the workshop are also directly relevant to the ongoing reform of research assessment and other current developments on recognition and rewards in academia. The workshop may help research performing institutions raise awareness and facilitate discussion on these topics.

1.4 Practicalities

This chapter covers some practicalities about the organisation of this specific workshop. Note that a general knowledge of how to run a workshop (venue booking, organisation, announcement, registrations, feedback and evaluation etc.) is assumed, so only topics specific to this particular workshop are highlighted.

1.4.1 Duration

110 min.

1.4.2 Audience

Target audience of the workshop

Given that the workshop is about the diversity of roles and contributions to research, it is important that the audience reflects that diversity and is as inclusive as possible. As such, it ideally includes researchers (including PhD candidates), research team leaders, various professional support staff (including data professionals, legal experts, ethics advisors, project management, HR talent development etc.) and decision-makers.

Ideal composition of the organisers' team

Ideally, the team of organisers is also composed of individuals with diverse roles and experiences, so they can relate with the audience and drive the discussion. To the extent possible, the team of organisers should be composed of researchers at various career levels, and have a diverse representation of professional support staff.

1.4.3 Roles during the workshop

Apart from regular participants, to smoothly run the workshop we suggest that the following roles are appointed:

Chairperson

- Welcoming the participants, keeping an eye on the time and smooth progress of the agenda, closing the workshop.
- Most likely a member of the organisation team.

Presenter

- Person (or people) introducing the slide deck and the activity.
- Most likely a member(s) of the organisation team.

Moderators

- People facilitating the discussion within the breakout groups, ensuring inclusivity and respect, guiding the participants, and ensuring that rapporteurs are appointed (if need be).
- Can be a member(s) of the organisation team or a volunteer(s) from the participants.
- For an effective moderation of the breakout groups, as well as to emphasise the team aspect, we suggest having two workshop moderators per breakout group, ideally composed of an academic and a professional support staff.

Rapporteurs

- People who will report from the breakout group discussion in the plenary session.
- Ideally volunteer(s) from the participants.

1.4.4 Break-out Groups

Participants will work in break-out groups. In advance of the workshop, decide how many participants you wish to have in your workshop and consequently, how many break-out groups you are willing to support. We recommend that the maximum group size doesn't exceed 8 participants per group to facilitate engaging and inclusive discussions.

More information about break-out discussion facilitation can be found in the *Activity* section.

1.4.5 Requirements

We suggest to have the following items available for the workshop:

- A large screen / projector
- Print out an *Activity Sheet* for each group (ideally on a large format such as A0). Alternatively you can use whiteboards or flip charts.

Hint: If you don't have the opportunity to print the large activity sheets, you can also use a flip chart paper. If you lay that out on the table, people around it can each fill in their comments. This way the group works more democratically than while using the standing flip chart.

- Marker pens for participants
- Tables set up for the breakout groups
- Timer and whistle to signal time is up (optional)

1.5 Agenda

This section outlines the agenda for the workshop with some practical suggestions for the organisers (in red). The agenda can be used as a template for a running sheet for the organisers during the workshop.

1.5.1 Last minute checks

-15 — 0 min

Attention:

- Ensure that spaces for the breakout groups are arranged (*activity sheets*, marker pens, tables and chairs).
- Decide which breakout groups are supported by whom.

1.5.2 Introduction of the workshop

0 — 10 min

1. Objectives of the workshop and expected outcomes

Hint: You can re-use the introductory slides from the *Slide Deck*.

2. Quick ice-breaker

Hint: Get to know the audience and their expectations with a quiz (e.g. [Mentimeter](#)).

Example questions:

- Who are you? (Researcher / Teacher / Academic / Professional Support Staff / Both / Other)
 - How many years of professional/academic experience do you have?
 - What is your field of expertise?
 - Why are you attending this session?
-

1.5.3 Introduction of the scenario and the activity

10 — 15 min

1. Explanation the scenario and outline the breakout session

Hint: You can re-use the slides from the *Slide Deck* to introduce the *Scenario* and the *Activity*.

2. Explanation of the roles (*moderators* and *rapporteurs*)

Hint:

- See the *Practicalities* section for more details.
 - Observe the discussions.
 - Stimulate the quite tables.
 - Help answer any questions during the discussion.
-

1.5.4 Breakout session

15 — 60 min

Attention:

- Appoint a moderator.
- Appoint a rapporteur.

- The chair person will instruct the groups every 10 min to move on to the next question.

Part 1: Ideal World

1. What are the important aspects in this project? (10 min)

Hint: For instance, things you need to manage, societal impact, scientific impact, open science, publicity, economic gains, etc. Try to make them as concrete as possible.

2. What skills / roles are needed to address these aspects? (10 min)

Hint: Try to group the skills / roles per aspect. Many-to-many connections are possible.

Part 2: Reality

1. Do people with those skills / roles exist? Do you know where to find them? (10 min)

Hint: Think about your own situation, e.g. for a certain skill / role identified. Do people know if it exists in their institution? Do people know how to approach those groups? etc.

2. Can you successfully include them in the project? How? (10 min)

Hint: If you find the skills / roles in your institution, what are the conditions of including them in the research project?

1.5.5 Break

60 — 70 min

1.5.6 Reporting back

70 — 85 min

1. Groups present summary of their discussions

Hint: x min per group, depending on the total number of groups.

2. General discussion about how the breakout session went.

Hint: Keep it very brief.

1.5.7 Plenary discussion

85 — 105 min

1. What can you do today to address the challenges?

Hint:

- Practical tips.
 - Creative ideas.
 - You may run an online survey (e.g. Mentimeter) to end the workshop, for example:
 - What is the most important take-away from the workshop for you?
 - What actions can you take today that would make your own environment more inclusive and appreciative?
-

2. What can your organisation do today?

1.5.8 Closing

105 — 110 min

Hint:

- Any take-away messages?
 - Any follow up activities?
 - Final take-home message: **Start acting today!**
-

1.6 Scenario

This document helps to create scenarios of research cases that can be discussed within a workshop. We present the original scenario and questions used in our workshop and the rationale behind it. We also generalise a list of core elements that can be selected to construct new scenarios.

1.6.1 Original scenario

This is the scenario we drafted for the workshop.

Magic Mirror (M&M)

The Magic Mirror (M&M) project aims to develop a personalised health mirror. You look in a mirror every day, the mirror *monitors your health* based on your look and not only *gives you health tips* (e.g. sleep more, drink more water), but also *tells you which diseases you might have* and *reports to your GP*.

You are partnering with other institutions and commercial partners to develop, test and bring this product to the market. The consortium is composed of the following partners:

- 3 universities (design, develop, test the product)

- 1 industrial partner (co-design, develop, sell the product)
 - 1 health insurer (co-design, consume data)
 - 1 NGO (test, sell, use the product)
 - 1 Patient group (co-design, development, test the product)
 - Citizens (co-design, test the product)
-

In this scenario, the research topic is in the domain of health care. We chose to set up a large consortium with various types of stakeholders, including higher education institution, commercial companies, non-profit organisations, and individuals. Given the research domain and consortium set up, it requires numerous areas of expertise to handle, among others, privacy, ethics, legal and security issues.

1.6.2 Core elements of a suitable scenario

It is important to design your scenario with a certain level of complexity. The complexity can be related to the number and diversity of stakeholders involved in the research project and/or the stage(s) of the research life cycle the scenario focuses on.

The **number and types of stakeholders** that are involved in the research activities have an influence on the research management. It is more likely that a project of a smaller size with similar types of stakeholders is easier to manage than a larger project, with different types of organisations and participants involved. In order to provide an illustrative case for the importance of diverse contributions and skills for achieving research objectives, it is preferable to develop a scenario which involves different types of stakeholders (e.g. public or private organisations, researchers, engineers, data stewards, lawyers, communication experts etc.).

Activities and objectives vary through **the stages of the research life cycle**. A typical research lifecycle includes:

- Identifying research question and objective
- Securing funding
- Literature review
- Research design
- Data collection
- Research analysis
- Dissemination of research outputs
- Valorisation

Attention should also be paid to **domain-specific issues** where the complexity lies.

You are free to design your scenario to cover one or multiple (or all) research stages that suit your purpose. In each research stage, different activities can take place which require different types of expertise (non-traditional researchers). It is ideal that your scenario could address issues that are associated with the research stage covered and domain specific issues. You could consider the areas of expertise and corresponding roles from the following table:

Areas of expertise	Roles
Privacy and security	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Privacy and compliance officer • Data protection officer • Legal counsel • Information security specialist • Knowledge security officer • Cybersecurity analyst • IT security specialist
Ethics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research ethics committee member • Research ethics board member • Ethicist / Ethics adviser • Diversity and inclusion officer
Commercialisation / valorisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Business developer • Intellectual property specialist • Legal counsel • Technology transfer officer • Entrepreneurship advisor • Market and investment analysts • Product developer • Marketing and sales professionals
Citizen science / societal engagement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Community Engagement Specialist • Community Manager • Publication engagement officer • Participatory research manager
Communication, education and outreach	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communication Specialist • Science writer / editor • Event manager • Education & outreach coordinator
Data and software	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data steward • Data manager • Data curator • Data scientist • Research software engineer
Project administration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project manager • Finance / business control • Contract manager • Research administrator
Project funding	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Grants officer • Grants adviser • Policy and strategy adviser
Infrastructure and instrumentation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research infrastructure developer
1.6. Scenario	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research application manager • Instrumentation engineer • Technician • Laboratory Manager • Infrastructure manager

1.7 Activity

This section describes the main interactive activity during the workshop, with step-by-step instructions.

1.7.1 Guided break-out group discussion

Attention: Ask the participants to form break-out groups and work on the given scenario.

Hint: The questions we used during the workshop to steer the discussions are listed below, which you might use as an inspiration in your session.

Hint: Set a timer of 10 minutes for discussing each question.

Ideal world

To facilitate the discussions during the breakout session, ask the participants to first imagine that they are in the *ideal world situation*. They can build the ideal team they need for the task by not thinking about any limitations (e.g. budget, etc.). The breakout groups are given two questions:

- **What are the important aspects in this project?**

With this question, ask participants to discuss things they, as a team, need to manage regarding societal impact, scientific impact, open science, publicity, economic gains and other related aspects, and try to make the list as concrete as possible.

- **What skills / roles are needed to address these aspects?**

Based on the aspects identified in the previous question, the participants need to make a list of relevant skills and/or roles per aspect. They are free to draw many-to-many connections between the aspects and the skills/roles, if possible.

Reality

Then invite the participants to bring the ideal situation discussed back to the reality and asked them the following questions:

- **Do people with those skills / roles exist? Do you know where to find them?**

The participants are encouraged to think about their own situation, e.g. for a certain skill/role identified, do people know if it exists in their institution, do people know how to approach those groups, etc.

- **Can you successfully include them in the project? How?**

If you find the skills/roles in your institution, what are the conditions of including them in the research project.

1.7.2 Reporting

After the guided break-out group discussion, ask the rapporteurs from each group to give a brief summary of their discussion. Subsequently, briefly reflect on how the breakout session went.

1.7.3 Plenary discussion

Wrap up the workshop with a plenary session focused on practical implications of the discussion. Ask the participants to think about practical tips or creative ideas that they can use immediately in their work.

Instead of open discussion, it is also recommended to run an online survey (e.g. Mentimeter) at the end of the workshop, some exemplary questions could be:

- What can you do today to address the challenges?
- What can your organisation do today?
- What is the most important take-away from the workshop for you?
- What actions can you take today that make your own work environment more inclusive and appreciative?

1.8 Slide Deck

[Download as PDF](#)

[Download as PPTX](#)

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Building Research **Dream Teams**

How to build team science and how to collaborate with not so obvious others

★ Dream team behind this workshop

Team science is the collaborative effort to address a scientific challenge that leverages the strengths and expertise of professionals trained in different fields.

The sharp distinction between 'academics' and 'support staff' is a barrier to effective research because it discourages a culture of collaboration and appreciation of a **diversity of roles and contributions**.

<https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-022-01081-8>

🔗 Online quiz

Let's get to know you a little better!

● Outline of the workshop

- Introduction (15 min)
- Breakout: Build your dream team (45 min)
- Break (10 min)
- Reporting back (15 min)
- Panel discussion (20 min)
- Closing remarks (5 min)

1 ● What is team science?

★ The keyword is **collaboration**

- Between researchers from different disciplines
- Between researchers, industry and other societal partners
- Between academic and professional support staff

2 ● Time to rethink the divide between academic and support staff

★ Main goals of this workshop

- Get researchers and professional support staff together in one room collaboratively thinking about the skills and roles needed for effectively tackling complex research questions.
- Start the discussion and raise awareness of the many skills, experiences and roles (some of which may be behind-the-scenes) that contribute to the success of the research system.

● Outline of the workshop

- Introduction (15 min)
- Breakout: Build your dream team (45 min)
- Break (10 min)

1.9 Activity Sheet

Download as PDF

<p>Ideal world What are the important aspects in this project? 10 min <i>For instance, things you need to manage, societal impact, scientific impact, open science, publicity, economic gains, etc. Try to make them as concrete as possible.</i></p>	<p>Ideal World What skills / roles are needed to address these aspects? 10 min <i>Try to group the skills / roles per aspect. Many-to-many connection is possible.</i></p>
<p>Reality Do people with those skills / roles exist? Do you know where to find them? 10 min <i>Think about your own situation, e.g. for a certain skill / role identified. Does it exist in your institution? Do you know how to approach those groups? etc. As concrete as possible.</i></p>	<p>Reality Can you successfully include them in the project? 10 min <i>If you find the skills / roles in your institution, what are the conditions for including them in the research project?</i></p>

1.10 Invitation to collaborate

If you decide to run a similar workshop, we would love to hear from you. We invite you to share your own experiences and materials with the community. We all benefit from each other's resources and experiences. Through collaboration we can keep improving these materials.

That's why we chose to host the toolkit on GitHub to make sure that anyone can easily build on and further develop the toolkit. You can contribute as little or as much as you want. You can start by making a comment on the resources, sharing your observations and experiences, improving the materials we have already made available, adding your own materials (for example, your own slides, new scenarios, modified agendas) or starting a discussion.

Link to the GitHub repository: <https://github.com/research-dream-team/toolkit>

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